

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE CONTENT OF HEAVY METALS IN SOILS AND VEGETATION OF RAILWAY STATIONS IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

This study determined the concentrations of seven heavy metals: cadmium, lead, copper, manganese, nickel, cobalt, and zinc, in the soil and vegetation of seven railway stations in western Georgia. The analyses were conducted using acid digestion and atomic absorption spectrophotometry methods. This is the first determination of metal contents in soil and vegetation at Georgian railway stations in operation for over 150 years. It was established that the total content of metals in contaminated soils is higher than the background level. The loading and unloading stations of the port cities of Poti and Batumi are the most polluted. Based on the overall pollution level ($Z_c > 32$), they are classified as "moderately hazardous", even taking into account the sharp decline in transport traffic over the past 30 years. The elevated Z_c value ($Z_c = 53.67$) for the Senaki station is mainly due to a significant increase in manganese and lead levels. Pollution levels at the passenger stations of the resort town of Kobuleti and the small town of Abasha are classified as "permissible levels".

Keywords: Heavy metals, contamination, railway stations, soil, vegetation.

1. Introduction

Heavy metals are naturally present in soils as a result of soil-forming processes in low concentrations (less than 1000 mg/kg) and are mostly non-toxic (Kabata-Pendias and Pendias, 2001). They can mainly be of various anthropogenic origins and become more mobile and bioavailable in soils than as a result of natural soil-forming processes (Kuo et al., 1983). Sources of contamination can include traces from mines, leaded gasoline and lead-based paints, fertilizer use, discharge of wastes with high metal content, animal manure, bio-waste (sewage sludge), coal and other fuel combustion residues, petrochemicals, pesticides, and atmospheric deposition (Khan et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2010; Basta et al., 2005). In terms of their rate of release into the environment, metals form the following order: Cu, Pb, Co, Fe, and Zn.

The level of HM content in soils depends on the oxidation-reduction and acid-base properties of the latter, hydrothermal regime, humus content, and particle size distribution (Ilyin, 2012). To characterize the general contamination of the soil, it is advisable to monitor the gross amount of metals, since when developing maximum permissible concentrations (MPC) of HM and non-metals in soils, the level of content of their

gross forms is most widely used (Vodyanitsky, 2011, 2013; Ilyin, 2012). In addition, the gross content of metals reflects the potential level of contamination. The availability of elements for plants is determined by the existence of their mobile forms. Therefore, the content of mobile forms of heavy metals in the soil is the most important indicator characterizing the sanitary, hygienic and environmental situation in regions, especially with technogenically disturbed soils [<https://doi.org/10.23670/IRJ.2020.102.12.043>].

Most pollutants enter the soil during cargo transportation. One of the most powerful pollutants and suppliers of heavy metals to the soil is rail transport, which passes or is temporarily idle in large cities and capitals, thereby worsening their environmental situation. Over the past 20-25 years, rail transport has been perceived primarily as the main source of pollution with heavy metals, oil products, and pesticides [Chen et al., 2014; Dzierżanowski & Gawroński, 2012; Meng et al., 2018; Mętrak et al., 2015; Staszewski et al., 2015; Šeda et al., 2017; Stojic et al., 2017;]. Soil contamination with heavy metals on railways occurs in various ways: scattering of transported chemicals during transportation and accidents, spills of fuels and lubricants (petroleum products), abrasion of the running parts of rails and

cars, combustion products of locomotive fuel, the use of pesticides in agriculture (Kabata-Pendias A., 1989)

The distribution of heavy metals over the soil surface is determined by many factors: the characteristics of the pollution sources, the meteorological features of the region, geochemical factors, and the landscape situation as a whole (Baker, D. E. et al., 1975; Safadoust et al., 2025]. The most dangerous part of the pollution, easily accessible to plants, accumulating in the upper horizons of railway soils, are mobile forms of heavy metals (HM). Many researchers argue that HM concentration in soil samples taken in the space between rails may exceed the benchmarks ten times.

The Georgian Railway, which has been in operation for over 150 years, is currently one of the most important components of the Eurasian Transport Corridor and the shortest route linking Europe with Central Asia. However, during all these years of operation, no study has been conducted on the soil composition for heavy metal content and migration in the station areas, nor has the level of pollution or the risk to the surrounding flora and fauna been assessed.

Mobile forms of heavy metals (HMs) accumulate in railway soils in Georgia due to constant anthropogenic impacts, including wear of rails, sleepers, and lubricants, as well as the use of ballast materials (crushed stone), and vehicle emissions. The most dangerous contaminants are copper, zinc, lead, cadmium, and manganese. In Georgia's humid climate, these metals are converted into forms accessible to plants, facilitating their migration. Georgian soils, particularly in the Colchis Lowland, are often characterized by an acidic or slightly acidic reaction, which contributes to the increased mobility of many HMs. The main mobile metals include Pb, Zn, Cd, Cu, Mn, and Ni, which are released through fuel combustion and structural wear. The greatest accumulation is observed directly in the ballast layer and adjacent soils. Metals are present in the form of exchangeable, water-soluble and acid-soluble compounds (extracted with 1 N HCl or ammonium acetate buffer).

It is known that overall soil contamination is characterized by the gross content of heavy metals, while the availability of elements to plants is determined by their mobile forms. The gross metal content reflects the potential level of contamination. Contamination by mobile forms of heavy metals is the most dangerous phenomenon, as it is in this form that plants can assimilate them and enter the food chain, increasing the environmental risk. They can also form complex organomineral compounds with humic acids, which become less mobile.

The purpose of this study is to assess heavy metal contamination levels (Pb, Cd, Cu, Mn, Fe, Ni, Zn and As) in the soils of seven passenger railway stations in West region of Georgia. Therefore, the research subject is the total content of HM in soils and vegetation. Sampling was carried out between and outside both rails up to the end of railway ties. The total content Pb, Zn, Cu, Ni, Co, Cd, Mn and As concentration in soils and in vegetation determined by the atomic absorption spectrometry method.

2. Research Objects and Methods

2.1. Sampling

During the field survey, over 50 soil samples collected. Soil samples collected from 21 sampling sites at a depth of 0-15 cm using a soil auger.

Each sample collected using the "envelope" principle from different points within the station premises: in the interrail space (center), as well as to the right and left at a distance of 20 meters from the center. Soil samples were stored in well-labelled plastic polythene containers and then transported to the laboratory for further soil treatment and analysis.

2.2. Sample Preparation

Sample storage and transportation for laboratory analysis (preparation and filling of containers, storage, sample filtration, etc.) were carried out and prepared in accordance with GOST 31861-2012. Plant samples for analysis were collected during summer period.

Particulate matter, plant roots, and pebbles removed from the air-dried sample. After loosening and sifting through a 1 mm sieve, the soil divided into four portions, and an average sample collected.

Acid digestion of plant and soil material was carried out in a sample decomposition system Microwave Pressure Digestion Labstation MWS-3, BERGHOF. Strong acid 1N HNO₃, ammonium acetate buffer solution with pH = 4.8 and water were used as extractants.

As a result of soil treatment with these solutions, ions and compounds of HMs pass into them, which can be combined into one set, called a fraction or group of HM compounds.

2.3. Chemical analyses

To determine the concentration of seven HM (Zn, Cu, Pb, Cd, Ni, Co, and Mn) a soil subsample of 0.5 g (0.001 g accuracy) was digested with HNO₃ and HCl (1:3) in Teflon bombs in an oven (140 °C), for 4 h, approximately according to the procedure described by Vallius Henry (1999). The solution was then evaporated to dryness and 5 mL of concentrated HNO₃ was added and evaporated again. The dried residue was dissolved in 5 mL of 0.1 M HNO₃ and placed in polyethylene tubes. Dilutions of ×10, ×100, and ×1000 were prepared and analyzed in a mass spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer AAnalyst 200) in accordance with ISO 8288-1986.

The results presented as mg/kg d.w. (d.w. – dry weight). The measurements replicated three times. Quality control assured by analyzing a certified reference material and “blanks”, according to the same procedure. Recoveries were in the range of 92–103%, depending on the individual metals. The precision, given as Relative Standard Deviation, was in the range of 3–5%.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Presence of Heavy Metals in Railway Station Soils

The key to effectively assessing soil contamination with heavy metals lies in the calculation and use of suitable contamination indices, which can be considered as a means of comprehensive geochemical assessment of the soil environment. A comprehensive approach to assessing soil quality using these indices is

also demonstrated by the ability to assess soil degradation due to long-term accumulation of heavy metals.

However, studying only the total heavy metal content in soil is insufficient. Such studies can only reflect the direction of certain processes, such as the migration of heavy metals in the soil. It is necessary to study the penetration of heavy metals in mobile form from the soil or through aerotechnogenic way into vegetation near railways.

The analysis results showed that contamination of soils and vegetation at railway stations in the Colchis

Plain and the Black Sea coast is multi-element in nature (Tables 1 and 2). For comparison, Table 3 provides the MAC values of heavy metals in soils according to WHO, EPA and Georgian Technical regulations on the quality of soil contamination. Soil pH and humus were defined too for each station (Table 4), as they determine the presence of mobile forms of heavy metals in soils.

Table 1.

The HM content in soils of railway stations in West Georgia

No	Site	Cu	Zn	Pb	Cd	Mn	Ni	Co	As	Total
1	Samtredia, L	74.0	108.8	44.0	3.4	1890	254.2	0.0	0.0	2374.4
2	Samtredia, C	142.6	164.0	87.4	2.6	8940	214.8	0.0	0.0	9551.4
3	Samtredia, R	47.6	240.2	162.0	2.8	1786	125.4	0.0	0.0	2364.0
4	Senaki, L	59.8	95.8	61.8	2.2	2136	186.2	0.0	0.0	2541.6
5	Senaki, C	248.0	105.6	476.2	2.8	10000	220.8	0.0	0.0	11053.4
6	Senaki, R	302.8	145.8	63.6	0.8	7236	189.4	0.0	0.0	7938.4
7	Poti, L	1064.0	339.6	49.2	0.1	1930	82.0	0.0	0.0	3464.9
8	Poti, C	257.4	144.7	149.3	1.5	6619	147.3	75.3	0.0	7394.5
9	Poti, R	42.2	70.7	19.7	1.4	5767	139.1	112.1	0.0	6151.2
10	Batumi, L	154.9	278.5	40.4	1.6	5700	338.4	71.3	-	6585.1
11	Batumi, C	115.2	193.6	63.8	1.9	6195	191.8	128.2	-	6889.6
12	Batumi, R	134.5	145.3	35.6	1.2	5497	223.7	81.8	-	6119.1
13	Zestaphoni, L	99.8	1075	54.1	2.1	5024	265.7	107.3	-	6628.0
14	Zestaphoni, C	59.8	72.4	27.8	2.1	6423	184.6	124.1	-	6893.8
15	Zestaphoni, R	65.3	95.7	29.1	2	5181	140.1	119	0.0	5632.2
16	Kobuleti, L	83.3	84.3	68.5	2.6	1127	237.5	160.2	0.0	1763.4
17	Kobuleti, C	161.6	110.3	49.9	2.5	1558	363.7	249.7	0.0	2495.7
18	Kobuleti, R	152	131.6	52.3	0	1233	0	0	0.0	1568.9
19	Abasha, L	94.6	78	40.4	0	988	0	0	0.0	1201.0
20	Abasha, C	88.2	82.4	40	0	1024	0	0	0.0	1234.6
21	Abasha, R	86.4	83	35.1	0	1058	0	0	-	1262.5

Table 2.

The content of some HM in vegetation of railway stations of West Georgia

No	Site	Cu	Zn	Pb	Mn	As
1	Samtredia, R	12.46	39.70	5.80	74.80	0
2	Samtredia, L	14.07	13.77	7.68	46.02	0
3	Zestaphoni, R	11.71	14.70	7.84	33.00	0
4	Zestaphoni, L	12.74	38.10	6.56	7.90	-
5	Abasha, L	15.15	14.42	6.28	86.60	0
6	Senaki, R	19.28	14.66	8.19	61.20	-
7	Senaki, L	7.14	15.27	11.05	84.20	0
8	Poti, R	20.53	15.33	8.52	8.43	-
9	Poti, L	37.98	13.77	7.90	15.00	0
10	Kobuleti, R	15.78	15.17	6.54	47.37	-
11	Batumi, R	24.18	11.70	9.74	125.30	0
12	Batumi, L	17.73	13.31	10.56	7.26	-

Table 3.

MPC of some heavy metals according to World Health Organization (WHO), the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) * and Georgian Technical regulations on the quality of soil contamination**

HM	As	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn
*	20	3	50	100	100	50000	2000	50	100	200
**	20	1	35	65	150	40000	2500	150	50	200

*- World Health Organization (WHO), the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA);

** - <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/download/6666330/0/1>.

3.2. Presence of Heavy Metals in railway station vegetation

According to the data in Tables 1 and 2, the content of the four analyzed HMs in the plants near the railway stations is significantly lower – five to seven times, and sometimes orders of magnitude lower – than in the soils of the railway stations. For example, in Senaki, the content of zinc, lead, copper and manganese in the soil exceeds their content in plants by 7, 10, 10 and 35 times, respectively. In Zestafoni, this ratio is as follows: Zn: Cu: Pb: Mn = 6: 5: 3: 150; At the final station of the route, Batumi, Zn: Cu: Pb: Mn = 11: 4: 4: 44. And at the vegetation-rich Black Sea station of Kobuleti, this ratio is: 8: 9: 8: 26. The given ratios show that manganese is least characterized by the formation of mobile forms capable of penetrating plants. This is confirmed by early data [Yu. V. Alekseev, 1987], according to which the phytotoxicity of manganese found in the soil is strongly related to its pH and redox potential. For example, in soils with a pH below 5.5, manganese is in a soluble form, and at pH 5.7 and 7.5, the transformation of Mn²⁺ into Mn⁴⁺ limits its mobility due to the formation of insoluble forms.

It is known that most heavy metals are more mobile in soils within a pH range of 4-4.5 [Yu. V. Alekseev, 1987]. Many heavy metals can accumulate in plants (agricultural crops) and, accordingly, become involved in the “plant-human”; “plant-animal-human” system.

Zinc has the highest content of mobile forms in railway soils [Avdoschenko et al., 2020], and the toxic effect of its high concentrations increases as soil pH decreases and humus increases [A. Samarska et al., 2020]. Arsenic was not detected in either the soils or the vegetation near railway stations. Perhaps, As concentration was below the limit of detection. The railway ballast cannot be considered as a serious source of As. Earlier

Wiłkomirski et al. [2013] showed also that the soil contamination with arsenic in the area of the tracks is rather low. According to Chinese researchers [Zhang et al., 2013], lead is one of the main pollutants of railway infrastructure, along with cadmium and zinc. We found that lead is present in the soils of virtually all railway stations, with a maximum content of 200 mg/kg in Senaki and a minimum of 37 mg/kg in Zestafoni. The levels of other metals are within the maximum permissible concentration limits.

Cu emission (on the electrified railways) is considered as the friction in the “pantograph-contact wire” system. The other is the abrasion of brakes and rails. The content of Cu do not exceeds MPC in any station according to new norms (see table 3), although it is common knowledge that railway stones are the significant sources of copper and nickel [Burkhardt et al., 2008; Liu et al, 2009; Wiłkomirski et al., 2011; Samarska et.al. 2020].

The data obtained (Table 4 and Fig. 1) indicate that the railway station in the port city of Poti has the highest environmental risk (total pollution of 7280 mg/kg), with the highest pH and low humus content. This station serves both freight and passengers, and the pollution level is primarily due to loading and unloading processes. Senaki follows, with pollution primarily due to high manganese levels. The soil conditions at the stations in the small town of Abasha and the resort town of Kobuleti correspond to low environmental risk and low pollution levels, as these stations served as passenger stations, and pollution occurs primarily due to wheel friction on the rails, pantographs, and overhead contact lines, as well as the possible use of pesticides. pH values range from 6-8, and humus levels (Table 4) are fairly close, so they can be considered to have no significant impact on pollution.

Table 4.

Average values and humus of stations' soils

No	Station	pH	Humus, %
1	Zestaphoni	6.43	5.91 c M
2	Samtredia	7.09	6.34
3	Abasha	7.06	3.18
4	Senaki	6.76	4.07
5	Poti	7.90	2.42
6	Kobuleti	6.02	6.09
7	Batumi	7.37	8.11

Fig. 1. Diagram of total pollution of the stations

3.3. Contamination Coefficient and total pollution

To assess the level of metal contamination in soils, the concentration coefficient K_c was calculated. This coefficient represents the ratio of the metal concentration in the soil of the studied area to its background value or MAC [MU 2.1.7.730-99. Hygienic assessment of soil quality in populated areas]: $K_c = C_i/MAC$, and the total contamination Z_c is determined by the following expression:

$$Z_c = \sum K_{ci} - (n-1),$$

where K_{ci} is the element's contamination coefficient and n is the number of elements. For our calculations, we used the background value, not the MAC, since the HM contamination is anthropogenic, but all the fixed elements are of natural origin. The calculated contamination coefficients and the total contamination of each station are presented in Table 5.

Table 5.

Contamination coefficients and total contamination of railway stations

Station	K_c (Cu)	K_c (Zn)	K_c (Pb)	K_c (Cd)	K_c (Mn)	K_c (Ni)	K_c (Co)	Z_c
Samtredia	3.52	2.85	8.15	0.29	5.26	6.6	0	20.96
Senaki	7.31	3.89	16.67	16.63	8.07	6.8	0	53.37
Poti	7.99	1.93	6.06	10	8.46	4.1	1.87	34.91
Batumi	2.45	8.34	3.91	16	7.25	7.4	1.87	27.92
Zestaphoni	2.99	16.56	3.08	0.2	6.93	6.6	2.33	32.69
Kobuleti	5.29	4.26	4.74	0.17	1.63	6.7	2.73	19.52
Abasha	3.59	3.24	3.21	0	1.28	0.0	0	5.32

To assess the risk of soil contamination with a complex of elements based on the Z -value, a gradation scale in accordance with "MU 2.1.7.730-99. Hygienic Assessment of Soil Quality in Populated Areas" was used. It was found that the total contamination of the studied railway stations, with the exception of Abasha station, whose total contamination level does not exceed the "permissible" level with $Z_c < 16$. Kobuleti, Samtredia and Batumi stations are classified as

"moderately hazardous," while the others are classified as "hazardous," with Z_c ranging from 32.69 to 53.37. According to calculated total contamination Z_c the following sequence of railway stations in Western Georgia was obtained: Senaki > Poti > Zestaphoni > Batumi > Samtredia > Kobuleti > Abasha (fig.2), that distinguishes it from dependence, obtained on the base of summarized total HM content (fig.1).

Fig. 2. Diagram of total pollution of the stations, calculated from pollution coefficients

4. Conclusion

At the first time it was determined the content of HM in railway stations of West Georgia. It was established that the total content of metals in contaminated soils is higher than the background level. The elements form a descending series according to their total concentration: Mn > Zn > Cu > Ni > Pb > Co > Cd. The sequence of railway stations in Western Georgia according to total contamination was defined: Senaki > Poti > Batumi > Zestaphoni > Samtredia > Kobuleti > Abasha. Senaki is the most polluted, while Abasha is the least. The total concentration of all heavy metals exceeds background levels by several times, and in rare cases prevails within the maximum permissible concentration limits.

Generally, pollution levels are classified as "acceptable" or "moderately hazardous." Only station Senaki can be classified as "hazardous."

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